
**Participatory Communication and Stakeholders' Perception of Delivery of
Right of Way for Infrastructural Projects in Lagos State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

This paper draws on in-depth field work in Lagos, Nigeria to describe the process of *right of way* delivery in Lagos State and explain the influence of participatory communication on stakeholders' perception of the process being carried out through the ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development. The method of study adopted is ethnography. The paper situated Right of Way delivery within the precinct of development and Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 11). It further examined stakeholders' preferred information sources and their views about the level of inclusiveness of the process of freeing setbacks of public road projects of encumbrances. The researchers posited that by offering instant feedback, face-to-face physical dialogues were effective in getting the buy-in of people whose property were affected. In conclusion, the researchers emphasised compliance with the right of way of infrastructure to enable Lagos State Government achieve the THEME (Transportation and Traffic Management; Health and Environment; Education and Technology; Making Lagos State a 21st Century Megacity, Entertainment & Tourism and Security and Governance) agenda. It was, therefore, recommended that government should not relent in ensuring that both traditional and digital media approaches are used in creating awareness for members of the public regarding the Right of Way of Government in order to facilitate the provision of social infrastructure for the betterment of the society.

Keywords: Participatory Communication, *Right of Way*, Perception and Stakeholders Engagement, SDG 11.

Introduction

The Lagos state Government in upholding its THEMES plus agenda, particularly the Making Lagos A 21st Century Economic pillar of this blueprint, has to make provision for infrastructure such as road networks, hospitals, schools and the likes, to cater to the needs of its over 22million population (Lagos Investment Deal Book, p.17). In doing this, property within the alignment of proposed road infrastructure must be cleared to accommodate the infrastructure. This makes serious demands on the coping abilities of the people whose property are to be affected. Sanusi (2021) in "What Lagosians Must Know about *Right of Way*, Infrastructure Development in Lagos" notes that infrastructural developments, ranging from road construction, public utilities and urban renewal projects come with some pains, where project sites have to be cleared of encumbrances. He goes on to define Right of Way as the space allowed on either side of

a public infrastructure for its management and as a condition precedent to the execution of public infrastructure projects in Lagos State. According to the author, *right of way* involves the determination, beforehand, of the alignments and the actual right of way of the proposed infrastructure, which include roads, bridges, drainage and buildings. A former Commissioner for Physical Planning and Urban Development, Dr. Idris Salako asserts that “the delivery of right of way for public projects is a pro-development endeavour with the ultimate relief of ease of connectivity and socioeconomic development that are bound to sprout as a result of the road construction” (Sanusi, 2021).

Governments provide public infrastructure, in line with the Sustainable Development Goal 11, which is about making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable. In receiving the social amenities within their communities, people whose buildings/ structures fall within the alignment of the public infrastructure being provided usually have to sacrifice by having their property removed for the infrastructure to birth. However, the intent of government is not to destroy but to engender development by providing the needed infrastructure in public interest. However, the process of establishing or reclaiming the right of way of public infrastructure inexorably necessitates dislocation through the removal of property from the right of way.

The establishment of right of way is a major task carried out in Lagos State through the Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development to pave way for the seamless execution of public projects and this is usually done following a process involving stakeholders’ engagement. Stakeholders’ engagement by the government is important in influencing what meaning stakeholders construe of the process as buttressed by participatory epistemology (Tarnas, 1991). Kim & Ball-Rokeach (2006) in looking at engagement of stakeholders, focused on communication structures and processes that negotiate 21st- century conditions of urban life, building on the rich tradition of research on communication and civic engagement. Participatory theorists such as Jorge Ferrer’s postulation of a “turn from intra-subjective experiences to participatory events in our understanding” of phenomenon is quite instructive in situating public engagement of people affected by *right of way* delivery in Lagos State (Ferrer, 2000). Tufte & Mefalopulos (2009) outline how participatory communication can promote mutual understanding, facilitate the empowerment of marginalised groups and produce wider social and political effects.

Stakeholders and *Right of Way* Delivery in Lagos State

Leveraging on Dr. F. Edward Freeman’s description of stakeholders in Aaltonen, Jaako & Tuomas (2008), the paper attempts an identification of the stakeholders of the Lagos State Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development especially in relation to *right of way* delivery. The stakeholder network is extensive and it includes investors, operators and others affected by the ministry’s activities. Examples are employees, property owners, community leaders, environmentalists, vendors, governmental agencies among others. Freeman (in Aaltonen *et al* 2008) identified stakeholder groups within an establishment and recommended ways of managing their interests and determining the

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level of importance of every stakeholder to the company. He argued that increasing value for stakeholders would improve the business in all aspects. According to Freeman, a company's stakeholders are "those groups without whose support the organisation would cease to exist" (Aaltonen, Jaako & Tuomas, 2008).

Thus stakeholders are the factors whose attitudes and actions have an impact on the organisation's success. Different stakeholders have different interests, attitudes and priorities irrespective of business focus or level of government (Hubacek, Guan & Barua, 2007). Beach, Brown & Keast (2008) identify stakeholders of Government agencies to be Government departments, Peak bodies and lobby groups. Others are staff, community, citizens, other levels of government and politicians. This indicates that there is a high level of stakeholder identification with groups who could potentially exert significant power over the agency.

It is also possible to view stakeholders in terms of interests and activities (Mariolina & Matteo, 2008). However, how most agencies make this differentiation and deal with the different stakeholder is germane. Ackermann & Eden (2011) maintained that managing the relationship between the numerous and usually competing various stakeholders is an important task for an organisation.

Thomas (2021) in Encyclopedia Britannica defines interest group or pressure group as "any association of individuals or organisations, usually formally organised, that, on the basis of one or more shared concerns, attempts to influence public policy in its favour." From the foregoing, one can deduce that the stakeholders of the Lagos State Government in relation to *right of way* are property owners/ developers and resident whose property/ structure encroach on the right of way of a given public project and are subject to removal by the state government. Other stakeholders are contractors involved in the construction, civil society organisations among others. Contractors in the process of executing the project interact directly with members of the benefiting community and would be interested in hitch-free project execution while the civil society and other interests groups are interested in how negative impacts of the projects can be minimised.

Participatory Process of Right of Way Delivery in Lagos State

According to Collins dictionary, *right of way* is a public path across private land. It is also defined as a strip of land that is used for a road, railway line or power line. The *right of way* is the total land area acquired for the construction of the roadway or other public infrastructure. Good practice is to acquire *right of way* wide enough to accommodate the ultimate development and all components of the road/project as well as all the elements of the roadway cross section. *right of way* also accommodates any future widening of the road and any public utility/ facilities that will be installed along the roadway. *Right of way* is the statutory route of a public infrastructure, designed and Geo-referenced by the Lagos State Office of Surveyor-General Odujibe. The Lagos State Physical Planning Permit Authority Regulations (2019) describes the Setback of properties of public utilities and *right of way* as follows –

(a) Highway and Roads:

- (i) 120m Right of Way – (60 metres from the median (centre) to the property line);

- (ii) 90m Right of Way - (45 metres from the median (centre) to the property line);
 - (iii) 60m Right of Way - (30metres from the median (centre) to the property line);
 - (iv) 30m Right of Way - (15metres from the median (centre) to the property line);
 - (v) 24m, 18m , 15m, 12m (12m, 9m, 7.5m and 6m right of ways respectively, from the centre to the property line as applicable);
- (b) Setback to Rail line: The minimum setback between a building and rail line shall not be less than twenty-one (21) metres from the edge of the outer rail line to the property line
- (c) Setback to Electric Power Network: The minimum horizontal distance between a building and the centre line of Electric overhead conductors shall not be less than the followings:
- (i) 0.415KV 6 metres;
 - (ii) 11 KV 6 metres;
 - (iii) 33 KV 10 metres;
 - (iv) 132 KV 20 metres;
 - (v) 330 KV 30 metres;
 - (vi) Sub-station Minimum of 12 metres from the Substation property boundary;
- (d) Setback to Gas and Oil pipelines: The minimum horizontal distance between the building line and Oil/Gas pipeline shall not be less than fifteen (15) metres from the outer edge of the alignment;
- (e) Setback to Water Bodies and Gorges:
- (i) Ocean and Sea: The minimum distance between any property and the ocean or sea shoreline shall not be less than one hundred and fifty (150) metres, in natural state (or otherwise where there is an embankment). In other areas it will be guided by the operative development plan for the area or shoreline protection;
 - (ii) Lagoon: The distance between any property and the Lagoon shore-line shall not be less than fifty (50) metres, or as may be specified from time to time, while, in special cases and under certain conditions, development may be allowed close to the edge of, and on the lagoon for tourism and recreational development purposes;
 - (iii) River and Creek: The distance between any building and river bank or creek shoreline shall not be less than fifteen (15) metres;
 - (iv) Gorge, Canal or Drainage: The distance between any building and the edge of a gorge, canal or drainage if defined by concrete live channel, shall not be less than ten (10) metres to the 23 building, or as may be specified by the relevant statutory body.
- (f) Setback to Cemetery: The setback of any development to cemetery shall maintain a minimum of Twenty Five (25) metres to the cemetery property boundary. Such cemetery shall be bounded by an access road or a buffer.
- (2) Without prejudice to Regulation 7 (1) above, the minimum distance of a building to any public utility may be subject to amendment from time to time as may be prescribed by the appropriate statutory bodies.

To allow for the smooth takeoff of any development project, the approved *right of way*, which, as a result of urbanisation, is usually encroached upon by residential and non-residential buildings, is established and delivered by the Lagos State Ministry of Physical

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Planning and Urban Development through a participatory process. The process usually includes the serving of statutory notices on all affected structures, the publication in national dailies of government intention to free the *right of way* of encroaching structures, holding of physical, face-to-face dialogue meetings, where government also communicates its intention and possible relief to the concerned stakeholders.

To achieve its goal of sustainable development, the Lagos State Government, through the Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development communicates its aims and intention to its stakeholders, particularly on *right of way* establishment and delivery and seeks their understanding and support for development projects in the state. In a charged atmosphere where the goal of communication is to seek understanding and accommodation for a supposedly negative action(at least in the audience's view) of removing structures on the right of way of a public project, the appropriateness of the channel of communication is a key element determining how efficient the flow of communication is. Communication is the process by which information is transmitted and understood between two or more people (McShare & Von Glinow, 2009). Witherspoon (1997), Von Krogh, George, Kazuo *et al* (2000) regard effective communication as the foundation of organisations, government inclusive. Organisations require communication to function effectively as they transfer information to their audiences about the organisations' focus, goals, objectives and activities (Farmer, Slater & Wright, 1998).

As cities worldwide grapple with issues such as population growth, resource management and infrastructure development, horizontal communication or bottom-up approach, as opposed to top-down approach to communication becomes a pivotal factor in not only disseminating information but also in shaping public opinion and policy discourse.

According to Paulo (1970), we can achieve sustainable action in development activities through dialogue or two-way communication. It is important to align social change with people's perception of their relations to government and the civil society, especially in pluralistic societies (Bennet, 2010). Bennet (2010) says, at stake is our understanding of the role of communication in shaping these political relations, and in shaping the attitudes of citizens about politics, government, and society itself.

However, for communication to be effective and result-oriented, Musa (2016) posits that the requirement for flexibility in aim, adaptability to change and stakeholders' concerns is necessary. Thus, stakeholder engagement strategies, which contrast sharply with the deficit model in communications research, ought to be adopted. The deficit model views communication as a one-way mechanism of educating an ignorant public (Meyer, 2016); it homogenizes the public, and ignores the critical role that peoples, local expertise, values, and experience can play in shaping and facilitating implementable policy interventions (Wynne, 2006).

Communicating *right of way* delivery in Lagos State combines both traditional and digital communication strategies which start with the use of both newspapers and digital platforms to acquaint members of the public of the proposed project with the need to remove encumbrances on its *right of way* and also give notice of physical, face-to-face stakeholders meeting, where people affected by the project are given opportunity to offer

suggestions. This method has been effective in building consensus and ownership of the project as both parties have had to shift grounds as required for the success of the project. For example, through such participatory process, government had sometimes agreed to reduce the *right of way* alignment, provide additional bridges or more access roads in response to the yearnings of stakeholders.

The process is also not without a hitch, especially where stakeholders remain adamant and unyielding to the proposed project in their community for the fear of being displaced as fallout of the Right of Way delivery. The engagement process in respect of the rehabilitation of Ijeododo road in Ojo Local Government Area, for instance, collapsed as residents would rather the government completely shifted the approved RoW of the proposed road. The result of the communication brake down was the suspension of the project since the year 2021. Another important aspect of Lagos State participatory approach to RoW delivery is the employment of the traditional mass media to proliferate messages of the face-to-face meetings and thereby extending the stakeholders engagement beyond the physical context.

In today's interconnected world, the media's influence on public perception, policy formulation and community engagement is undeniable. Through various forms such as print, broadcast and digital media, it has the potential to drive positive change and foster sustainable development in urban areas. By raising awareness and facilitating the dissemination of information, the media can encourage the implementation of sustainable practices, policies and initiatives at the local, national and global levels. Both traditional and digital media platforms significantly influence public perception and decision-making during the participatory process. Positive media representations can foster public trust, support and active engagement, encouraging communities to participate in sustainable development projects and advocate for inclusive urban planning practices (Glasgow & Wood, 2014). Conversely, negative or biased media coverage can evoke fear, skepticism, and resistance, hindering community participation and impeding the successful implementation of urban relocation initiatives (Entman, 2004). By shaping public narratives and influencing public discourse, both traditional and digital media have the power to sway public opinion and shape policy priorities, thereby impacting the trajectory of sustainable urban development (Habermas, 1989).

In line with the views of Lacy (2007) on media impacts, the ministry, by involving the use of newspapers, has been able to tap the advantage of comprehensive coverage and in-depth analysis to provide communities with a nuanced understanding of the benefits, challenges and implications of projects. Television news and documentaries offer visual narratives that can evoke empathy and understanding, fostering community engagement and support for sustainable development initiatives (Nerone, 2010). Radio broadcasts provide a platform for dialogue and discussion, enabling communities to voice their concerns and aspirations, thereby contributing to the formation of informed public opinion (Lilleker & Koc-Michalska, 2018).

In the digital age, the role of digital media platforms, including social media, websites, and mobile applications, has become increasingly prominent in shaping public perception. Digital media allows for real-time information sharing, interactive

communication, and community engagement, enabling diverse stakeholders to participate in discussions and contribute to the dialogue surrounding urban relocation (Chadwick, 2017). Social media platforms, in particular, provide avenues for communities to share their experiences, concerns, and aspirations, fostering a sense of shared identity and collective action (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Websites and mobile applications offer interactive resources and visual representations, empowering individuals to access information, participate in decision-making processes, and actively engage in sustainable urban development initiatives (Castells, 2010). An important element in civic engagement is communication structures, which include free, plural, and independent media systems, robust civil society and the legal and regulatory framework that enables or precludes the free flow of information from government to citizens and vice versa. These form the framework through which citizens and government can communicate and engage in dialogue. They are essential components of the so-called 'democratic public sphere,' and play an important role in forming public opinion (Comm GAP, 2007).

Theoretical Framework

The paper is based on the theoretical foundation of participatory communication theory and stakeholders' theory. The theory was developed by Paulo Freire in 1970. The focus of the participatory communication theory is improved quality of life achievable through horizontal dialogue and active participation in public life. The theory prescribes dialogue or two-way communication as a means to consensus for sustainable action in development activities. Tufte & Mefalopulos (2009) outline the importance of participatory communication in promoting mutual understanding, facilitating the empowerment of marginalised groups and producing wider social and political effects. According to Mefalopulos (2008, p.51), features of the participatory communication theory include 'emphasis on people, the endogenous vision of development and the attention to power and right issues.'

Participatory communication is an approach based on dialogue, which allows the sharing of information, perceptions and opinions among the various stakeholders and thereby facilitates their empowerment. It is not just the exchange of information and experiences: it is also the exploration and generation of new knowledge aimed at addressing situations that need to be improved. Participatory communication tends to be associated with community-driven development, but it could be used at any level of decision making (local, national, international) regardless of the diversity of groups involved. The theory assumes that genuine participation increases the sense of ownership by local stakeholders, thereby enhancing sustainability. To be genuinely participatory and truly effective, communication should occur among all parties affected, ensuring all have similar opportunities to influence the outcome of the initiative. Ideally, participatory communication should be part of the whole project process. The theory recognises the fact that full participation by all stakeholders in any step of the process is not possible and, in some cases probably not desirable. Broad consensus may be sufficient.

The second theoretical base for the paper is the stakeholder theory which concentrates on the audience or objects of engagement while the participatory theory

focuses on the process of engagement. The stakeholder theory is a theory of organisational management and business ethics that accounts for multiple constituencies impacted by business entities like employees, suppliers, local communities, creditors and others. It addresses morals and values in managing an organisation, such as those related to corporate social responsibility, market economy and social contract theory. Stakeholder theory views an organisation as a collection of various individual groups with different interests, and posits that business decisions should, as much as possible, consider the interests of this collective group and advance overall cooperation. Stakeholder theory was first described in 1983 by Dr. F. Edward Freeman, a Professor at the University of Virginia, in his landmark book, *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach* (Aaltonen, Jaako & Tuomas, 2008).

The theory views shareholders as just one of many stakeholders of an organisation. According to the theory, the stakeholder network is extensive and it includes investors, operators and others affected by the company. Examples are employees, environmentalists, vendors, governmental agencies among others. Freeman suggests that a company's real success lies in satisfying all its stakeholders, not just those who might profit from its stock. Unlike the shareholder theory of the early 20th century, which summarised the company's focus as profit to shareholders, the Stakeholder theory seeks to harmonise the interest of all as a factor for organisational success. Freeman identified stakeholder groups within an establishment and recommended ways of managing their interests and determining the level of importance of every stakeholder to the company. He argued that increasing value for stakeholders would improve the business in all aspects. According to Freeman, a company's stakeholders are "those groups without whose support the organisation would cease to exist." (Aaltonen, Jaako & Tuomas, 2008). These groups include customers, employees, suppliers, political action groups, environmental groups, local communities, the media, financial institutions, governmental groups among others. Thus the corporate environment is viewed as a network of related groups which must be considered and satisfied to ultimately keep the organisation healthy and successful.

From the foregoing, Stakeholders are the factors whose attitudes and actions have an impact on the organisation's success. Different stakeholders have different interests, attitudes and priorities.

Effective communication will ensure that stakeholders get useful and adequate information to build the required positive attitudes to the organisation or its project(s). The key principle of stakeholder engagement is communication concisely and consistently delivered to the targeted groups. The theory assumes that stakeholders have a vested interest in the organisation and its projects, and are therefore willing to be involved in the organisational process. Therefore, they need to be abreast of the goings on and this can be achieved through effective information dissemination to them. The theory seeks to encourage organisations to optimise stakeholders' relationship and thereby improve organisational efficiency. The use of Stakeholder theory spans many important fields such as project management, corporate social responsibility, strategic management, public relations and business ethics. McQuail (1987) defined theory as a set of ideals of

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varying status and origin which may explain or interpret some phenomenon. Thus, the Stakeholder theory partly explains why governments MDAs (Lagos State Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development inclusive) as service-oriented public institutions strive to carry along their stakeholders as the hallmark of their stewardship and transparency. The essence of the communication by the government or its agencies is to ensure popular participation and enlist the support of the audience or stakeholders. Thus the Stakeholders theory is instructive.

Methodology

Data in this report are based on 48 months ethnographic fieldwork (July 2019-July 2023) practically carried out from the placement of awareness creation newspaper publications and organisation of town hall meetings in which views of affected stakeholders were recorded by the ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development staff who engaged in the service of demolition notices and sometimes the demolition of encroaching structures. Responses to news and photo releases on *right of way* delivery were also monitored. In all, the Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development delivered 38 public project sites free of encumbrances within the stated period.

Findings and Discussion

The findings showed that there was proper stakeholders' identification by the ministry in its communication of the *right of way* delivery process, which starts with the mapping of the affected persons and followed by communication designs. Consequently, the ministry is able to effectively deploy the face-to-face meeting, social media and mass media as communication strategies in relating with its stakeholders regarding the delivery of *right of way*.

The ministry employs the traditional and digital media to pass information of its RoW activities while also relying on opinion leaders to boost information sharing in the different communities (the multi-step flow theory). Consequently, majority of stakeholders expressed that their main sources of information were physical notices served by ministry officials, followed by newspaper publications and town-hall meetings. In this manner, the stakeholders believed they were able to get information faster and directly from the ministry.

It was observed that the multichannel approach of the ministry allowed it to take advantage of the richness of these mediums. However, there was high preference among stakeholders for physical face-to-face meetings to other communication channels adopted by the Ministry, because it offers the opportunity for stakeholders to take part in the decision-making process through two-way communication, where the immediacy of feedback was present.

Stakeholders' meetings organised by the ministry allowed it to thoroughly iron out issues with the audience, while both parties could measure or assess the level of communication through verbal and non-verbal indicators like tone, voice pitches, facial expression and eye contacts among others. This explains the preference for the direct communication method.

By communicating gains of the project to stakeholders and offering them the relief of compensation for property demolished through a participatory process, the Lagos

State Government has been able to develop a sense of ownership of several projects in the people who sometimes ask for more roads, bridges and similar infrastructure despite being confronted by the reality of demolition of property. Out of *right of way* activities of the ministry, the writer could record only one inconclusive engagement process in which the people of Ijeododo community could not find a common ground with the government regarding the *right of way* alignment of a project in their area, thereby leading to the suspension of the proposed road project for the community.

It empowers stakeholders with knowledge of the project and what is expected of them as stakeholders while encouraging ownership of projects as the open communication fosters mutual respect and understanding. The method of communicating *right of way* delivery by the Lagos State Government ensures that the people are constantly engaged and this is in tandem with Mefalopulous's (2008, p.51) features of the theory of participatory communication, which include emphasis on people, the endogenous vision of development, and the attention to power and right issues. As espoused by Ibuot, Majemu & Nwantah (2021, p. 227), the Lagos State model fulfills the theory's two broad assumptions of participation and communication. The kind of participation fostered through the RoW delivery process in Lagos State differs from what Ibuot, Majemu & Nwantah (2021, p.227) classified as passive participation, where stakeholders are merely informed of what is happening or what has been decided; but suits Pretty, Gujit, Thompson & Scoones (1995, p.60) who advocated for consultative, functional and interactive participation. All said, participatory communication favours horizontal, two-way and interactive approach to communicating development. Engaging stakeholders is necessary to identify shared values and involve communities and social networks in decisions that will affect them (Adler & Goggin, 2005; Miranti & Evans, 2019). Meaningful stakeholder engagement can improve the effectiveness of containment measures (Renn, 2008; Renn & Walker, 2008) and encourage greater ownership of decisions with more chance of public cooperation (Head, 2004).

From the foregoing, the Lagos State Government should intensify efforts to deepen the participatory communication process by extending it to the actual establishment and geo-reference stage of *right of way*. When this is done, the process gains credibility and avoids the kind of disagreement in the Ijeododo case as the requirement of the emphasis on people and active participation would have been met.

The researchers identified the communication process employed by the Lagos State Government through the ministry of physical planning and urban development in delivering the Right of Way of public projects and also ascertained the preferred channels of getting information by those whose property are affected by the Right of Way delivery. It concludes that the methods adopted by the government in communicating issues around the delivery of Right of Way to the affected stakeholders were effective as it involves functional and interactive participation of stakeholders.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The researchers conclude that the participatory, bottom-up approach has proven effective for carrying the people along in executing development projects in Lagos State. The Lagos State Government's THEMES Plus agenda, particularly the focus on transforming Lagos into a 21st-century economic hub, requires extensive infrastructure development to

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support its large population. This development includes constructing road networks, hospitals and schools, which necessitates clearing properties within the proposed infrastructure alignment places. It, therefore, places significant demands on affected residents due to the inevitable difficulties and disruptions that accompany infrastructural projects, like road construction and urban renewal. The *right of way* is essential space allocated for managing public infrastructure and it involves pre-determining alignments and ensuring the *right of way* for infrastructures such as roads, bridges, and drainage systems. This underscores the reasons the *right of way* must be observed in order to assist pro-development efforts and ultimately enhance connectivity and socioeconomic growth which give arise to infrastructure projects.

Based on the foregoing, there is need for the development a robust communication plan to inform and engage affected residents well in advance of any infrastructural developments. This should include public meetings, informational sessions and digital platforms to ensure transparency as well as implementation of participatory approaches in planning and decision-making processes. This should involve engagement of community members in dialogues to better understand their concerns and incorporate their feedback into project plans.

By implementing these recommendations, the Lagos State Government can better manage the challenges associated with infrastructure development and ensure that the needs of its population are met while fostering a collaborative and inclusive approach to urban planning.

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